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ADMINISTRATIVE ACTIVITY AND MANAGEMENT IN EDUCATION
SOCIAL FACTORS

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Annotation: In this article, management activities in the educational system, the role of management, goals and tasks, principles, management social factors were discussed.

Key words: leader, management, management, quality, management culture, innovative approach, function, integrative quality.

Effectiveness in management activities of educational organization leaders conditions necessary for development:

- has an innovative structure and management process of educational institutions

approach as a complex pedagogical system;

- management culture, interpersonal and educational culture of the leader forming relationships based on scientifically based principles;

- the professional of the leader in the process of innovative activity of the educational organization

a scientific approach to his skills and thoughts about himself; management by leaders educational direction of activity, conceptual and programmatic pedagogical system implementation of mastery of management;

- innovative approaches in the process of managing an educational organization provide feedback on the results.

Today, the leaders of the organization are integrative of management functions characteristics describing the qualities: adaptation of organization management to internal and external changes, leadership corporate use of methods, mastering the principles of educational management and application, management and development of the educational institution indicates the designation based on the direction of improvement. Pre-school education direct leadership of the organization was carried out by the director. Employment of the head of a preschool educational organization is regulated by law with the Ministry of Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the prescribed manner

will be done by agreement. With the head of the State Preschool Education Organization The employment contract is concluded for one year. Qualification

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requirements for the position of head of a preschool educational organization determined by the Ministry of Pre-School Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Head of preschool education organization:

- Operates on behalf of a preschool education organization without a power of attorney, represents his interests in all institutions and organizations;
- The property of the preschool educational organization within the scope of the powers assigned to it disposes of;
- issues power of attorney;
- opens bank accounts;
- Recruitment and placement of employees of preschool education organization implements, encourages, takes disciplinary measures and they terminates employment contracts (contracts) concluded with;
- issues orders (orders) within the scope of his powers;
- The material basis for improving the work of preschool educational organizations proposals on strengthening, ensuring social protection of employees submits it to the higher public education management body for review;
- effective organization of protection of children's life and health, education process, state of financial and economic activity, material and technical base is responsible for strengthening and preservation of material wealth.

Preschool education organization is a complex network, the role of the principal in it, its activity is multifaceted.

Head - the organizer of the preschool education organization, head, a qualified pedagogue, whose work is aimed at children of preschool age aimed at fully solving the tasks of raising a perfect person. He is children in accordance with educational, pedagogical and hygienic requirements in institutions provides the necessary conditions for its implementation. In his team work creates a situation of goal-oriented focus. General guidance to them does. Head was accepted in his work by our state and the Ministry of Public Education follows the decision, laws and works creatively on himself.

High consciousness and political maturity, principles, to himself and subordinates

demandingness - these are the main requirements for the headmaster.

Correct, mutual relations in the team are the work and work of each employee ensures compliance with release discipline. The leadership position of the head is based on his ideological, spiritual-educational, political, legal Pedagogical knowledge

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always conscious of the level and regional skills to master the theory and practice of teaching children, current to know the tasks facing preschool education at the stage, from their own knowledge forces to use in practical activities. It is a program, methodical instruction, should be familiar with and follow regulatory documents. He is a pedagogue knowing the essence of the process and immediately eliminating its achievements and shortcomings it is necessary to take measures.

Head of preschool education organization Preschool education management bodies has a higher education and at least 5 years of teaching experience appointed from among the persons. Selection of personnel in preschool education organization, labor team, pre-school education

It is carried out by the administration with the participation of the activists of the organization's council. Before school the heads of the educational organization assess the professional skills of the personnel, the general educational skills, takes care of the regular growth of the general educational and cultural level: taking into account the qualifications of employees and the organization of preschool education based on their interests, moving them from place to place in a rational and timely manner ensures standing.

A reserve of personnel is formed in the pre-school education organization and is permanent with them work is carried out. The personal composition of the preschool education organization is as follows consists of: administrative group (principal, educator-stylist, household manager, senior medicine nurse), employees of pedagogy, medicine, service industries. Administration of pre-school education organization in cooperation with public organizations to achieve high results in raising children on the basis of self-management forms a stable labor team that is capable; personnel regularly improvement, pedagogical and service delivery, labor efficiency educates in the spirit of improvement, a sense of pride for one's team, chosen profession forms.

Heads of pre-school education organizations assess the professional skills of personnel, in general to regularly improve educational skills, general education and cultural level cares; taking into account the qualifications of employees and pre-school education Based on the interests of the organization, they are rationally and on time from place to place ensures that it is copied. For these purposes, the administration is spiritual and pedagogical ensures organic integration of the child with legal and economic education; conditions for improving the qualifications of employees directly in the preschool education organization creates, develops coaching

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action; at home and abroad provides information about achievements in pedagogical and other mixed subjects.

Pre-school education organizations together with public organizations provides optimal conditions for the attestation of its employees, provides them with the necessary methodological support in time.

Head - level of spiritual, political, legal, moral maturity, consciousness, enlightenment, civility, educating employees in the spirit of patriotism, honesty, conscientiousness, resistance to criticism, hard work and foresight features must be available.

Job Duties:

- Leading the general activities of the preschool education organization;
- organization of the pedagogical team and other employees to achieve high efficiency in educational work with children;
- modern forms of labor organization in the educational process use;
- state requirements for preparing children for primary school education monitoring the implementation of appropriate educational programs;
- strengthening of children's health, their pedagogy and hygiene requirements to ensure the creation of necessary conditions for appropriate education and training;
- leadership of the pedagogical council, issues of child education in the family organizing work with parents on;
- sanitary and hygienic requirements, labor protection, equipment and fire ensuring compliance with safety regulations;
- rational use of budget funds and care for the property of the institution to relate and others.

During the educational process, the teacher and the students exchange lively language and ideas understanding, sincere attitude, respect, cooperation in achieving the main goal is necessary. The content is shallow, detached from practical experience and life, general and dry a lecture that consists of exhortation and is conducted superficially for the sake of formality and other educational activities do not interest students, they are scientific and ideological does not provide adequate nutrition. Therefore, organize training sessions in this way It should be noted that under its influence, students have different views on this subject, scientific thoughts and beliefs need to be formed and formed. Education and upbringing higher effectiveness of the process, first of all, the teacher's scientific potential, reputation among young people,

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personal qualities, scientific talent, education experience and skills in the field and friendship established with students depends on the relationship.

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